

**ABIGBO SONG OF MBAISE: AN ANALYTICAL SURVEY OF ITS
NATIONAL SIGNIFICANCE**

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Abstract

This paper looks at the socio-cultural significance of the Abigbo Song of Mbaise people of Imo State. It traces the meaning and origin of Abigbo Song to the ancient time of the people. The writing looks at the traditional essence of the music and song in checking the social ills and other human excesses from the religious and political viewpoints. The songs are analyzed and interpreted in relation to what obtains in the contemporary society. The first song condemns some of the practices by some spiritual leaders who give Holy Communion to people with questionable character. The second song centres on civil disturbances in the country due to ethnic political and religious differences. The third song touches on corruption in all walks of life in Nigeria. While the fourth and last song dwells on the disappointment of the masses by the elected political class who do not live up to their pre-election promises to the people. The paper concludes, by identifying Abigbo Song as a weapon against the social and political ills that plague not only the immediate community of the artists but also the Nigeria nation by extension.